

SZ-100

Measurement Results

Date : 14 June 2025 14:01:20
 Measurement Type : Particle Size
 Sample Name : A1
 Scattering Angle : 90
 Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 2.027 mPa·s
 Transmission Intensity before Meas. : 25350
 Distribution Form : Standard
 Distribution Form(Dispersity) : Monodisperse
 Representation of Result : Scattering Light Intensity
 Count Rate : 169 kCPS

Calculation Results

Peak No.	S.P.Area Ratio	Mean	S. D.	Mode
1	1.00	787 nm	37 nm	68 nm
2	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
3	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
Total	1.00	787 nm	37 nm	68 nm

Cumulant Operations

Z-Average : 798 nm
 PI : 0.612

